

MA Miloš Bojčić
Faculty of Philosophy
University of Belgrade
milosbojic94@gmail.com

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Serbia and Venice during the reign of Stefan Dušan

ABSTRACT: This paper examines the relationship between Serbia and the Republic of Venice during the reign of King and Emperor Stefan Dušan. One of its aims is to highlight the distinct characteristics of Serbian-Venetian relations during this period, compared to earlier times, and to explore the reasons behind the Serbian ruler's efforts to elevate these relations to a higher level. To provide context, the introduction offers a brief overview of the ties between the Nemanjić dynasty and Venice. The study is structured geographically, focusing on the states that fell within the spheres of interest of both Venice and Serbia and whose political actions influenced Serbian-Venetian relations. These states include the Byzantine Empire, Hungary, and Bosnia. A separate section is dedicated to the economic dimension of their relationship, with special attention given to the cities of Dubrovnik and Kotor. From the Serbian perspective, relations with Venice were primarily driven by political motives—specifically, Dušan's hopes that Venice would support his ambitions to conquer Constantinople. Meanwhile, Venice's primary concern was trade and ensuring its uninterrupted flow. Both sides sought to achieve their respective goals through diplomatic missions, negotiations, and mediation.

KEYWORDS: Serbia, Venetian Republic, Byzantium, Bosnia, Dubrovnik, Kotor, Stefan Dušan, medieval diplomacy, embassies, mediations

Introduction

Due to the nature of the preserved historical sources and the political circumstances of the time, one of the most promising periods for scholarly research into Serbian-Venetian relations is the first half of the 14th century, covering the reigns of King Milutin, King Stefan Dečanski, and King and Emperor Stefan Dušan. From the very beginning of Milutin's rule, it is possible to trace the development of Serbian-Venetian relations, which gradually became more complex. However, there are still moments when historical sources remain silent on the interactions between the two states. During the reign of his successor, no significant changes occurred. However, under Stefan Dušan, both the nature and intensity of these relations transformed. In King Milutin's time, the Venetians primarily played two roles: as mediators in Serbian–Dubrovnik disputes and as merchants with vested interests in Serbia, which the Venetian government sought to protect. The situation remained largely the same under Stefan Dečanski. However, Dušan elevated the relationship between the two states to a higher level. For him, the Venetians were no longer just merchants or mediators in disputes—they were also potential allies. Under his son's rule, the situation changed. In 1358, the Venetians were expelled from the eastern Adriatic by the Treaty of Zadar, and for the next several decades, historical sources provide little information on relations between the two states.

No ruler of the Nemanjić dynasty had as extensive and multifaceted relations with Venice as Stefan Dušan. However, Serbian-Venetian ties can be traced back to the dynasty's founder, Stefan Nemanja. The war waged by the Venetians and Serbs against Byzantium in 1171–1172 represents the first recorded instance of military cooperation between the two states.¹ During the reign of Stefan Nemanjić, the son of Nemanja, the Venetians became the supreme overlords of Dubrovnik and a significant political force on the Balkan Peninsula. This was likely one of the reasons why Stefan the First-Crowned married Anna Dandolo, the

¹ *Историја српског народа, књ I: Од најстаријих времена до Маричке битке (1371)*, ур. Сима Ћирковић (Београд: Српска књижевна задруга, 1981), 210–211; Ћорђе Бубало, *Српска земља и поморска у доба владавине Немањића. Књ. 1, Од Сабора у Расу до Сабора у Дежеву* (Београд: Филип Вишњић, 2016), 61–62.

granddaughter of former Venetian Doge Enrico Dandolo, in the first half of 1217.² During the reign of King Uroš I, relations between Serbia and Venice were largely conducted through Dubrovnik, forming a triangular dynamic between the three states. These interactions became more intense during the rule of his son, King Milutin.

Throughout Milutin's reign—certainly in its first half and likely for its entirety—a form of monetary warfare took place between the two states. On multiple occasions, Venice attempted to counter the uncontrolled influx of allegedly devalued Serbian currency.³ The reign of King Milutin marks the first recorded instance of direct hostility between Serbia and Venice. In the first half of 1301, the people of Dubrovnik, supported by Venetian galleys and warriors from Zadar and Croatia, launched an attack on Kotor. This led to a brief war, followed by negotiations. Although initially hostile towards Serbia, the Venetians eventually took part in the negotiations. With their mediation, peace was concluded in the summer of 1302.⁴ According to the Dubrovnik chronicler Giunio Resti, a war broke out between Serbia and Dubrovnik in 1316. On that occasion, the Venetians once again acted as mediators, sending a diplomatic mission to Serbia.⁵ The following year saw another conflict between the two states, although it is possible that this was merely a

² Ивана Коматина, „Ана Даноло – прва српска краљица?“, *Зборник Матице српске за историју* 89 (2014), 19. It is possible that Vladislav, the son of King Dragutin, also married a Venetian woman. More about this: Александра Фостиков, Невен Исаиловић, „Уговор о веридби Владислава II Немањића и Констанце Морозини“, *Мешовита грађа*, књ. XXXIX (2018), 7–38.

³ More about this: Ружа Ђук, *Србија и Венеција у XIII и XIV веку* (Београд: Просвета, 1986), 22–35. and Вујадин Иванишевић, *Новчарство средњовековне Србије* (Београд: Стубови културе, 2001), 27–30, 33–42.

⁴ More about this: Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 35–37; Бариша Крекић, „Зашто је вођен и када је завршен рат Дубровника и Србије 1301–1302?“, *Зборник радова Византолошког института* 17 (1976), 417–422; Nebojša Porčić, „Peace Negotiations Between Serbia and Dubrovnik in 1301–1302: A Case Study in Medieval Diplomacy“, *Иницијал. Часопис за средњовековне студије* 1 (2013), 115–134; Небојша Порчић, Невен Исаиловић, „Папе, краљеви, моћници, комуне. Западна политика“, у *Свети краљ Милутин. Владар на раскршћима светова*, ур. Срђан Пириватрић, Смиља Марјановић-Душанић, Даница Поповић (Београд: Задужбина Светог манастира Хиландара, 2022), 162–163.

⁵ *Chronica Ragusina Junii Restii (ab origine urbis usque ad annum 1451) item Joannis Gundulae (1451–84)*, ed. Sp. Nodilo, *Zagrabiae* 1893, 106–107; Порчић, Исаиловић, „Западна политика“, 177–178.

continuation of the hostilities from 1316. Initially, the Venetians supported the people of Dubrovnik by supplying them with weapons and ships. However, they soon assumed the role of mediators once again, ultimately facilitating the conclusion of peace.⁶

There are few recorded instances of cooperation between King Milutin's Serbia and the Republic of Venice. On two occasions (1281–1282 and 1306–1308), both Serbia and Venice were part of anti-Byzantine coalitions, which ultimately failed to achieve their objectives.⁷ In 1313, Serbia and Venice shared a common enemy in Mladen II Šubić. On that occasion, King Milutin procured weapons from Venice, and it is possible that some form of alliance was established between Serbia and the Republic of Venice. However, there is insufficient evidence to confirm this with certainty.⁸ A similar situation occurred five years later when war once again broke out between King Milutin and Mladen II Šubić. The Serbian ruler purchased weapons in Venice and offered the Venetians an alliance. However, in the end, Venice's role in the conflict was limited to mediation.⁹

During the reign of Stefan Dečanski, the son and successor of Milutin, the Venetians primarily acted as mediators but occasionally played a more direct role in Serbian-Dubrovnik relations. Almost continuously from 1324 to 1327, tensions between Serbia and Dubrovnik flared, at times threatening to escalate into war. The Venetians repeatedly sent diplomatic missions to Serbia and, on several occasions, even prohibited their merchants from traveling there. The open war broke out in the second half of 1327. The Venetians once again acted as mediators, thus contributing to the achievement of peace, which was signed in the early autumn of the following year.¹⁰ In May 1330, the Serbian ruler sent a letter to Venice informing the doge that he guaranteed safe passage for Venetian merchants through Serbian territory. He assured them the

⁶ Ћук, *Србија и Венеција*, 40; Порчић, Исаиловић, „Западна политика“, 177–178.

⁷ Ћук, *Србија и Венеција*, 37–38; *Историја српског народа I*, 439, 455–456; Георгије Острогорски, *Историја Византије* (Београд: Српска књижевна задруга, 1959), 434; Порчић, Исаиловић, „Западна политика“, 149–151, 157, 169–173.

⁸ Михаило Динић, „Comes Constantinus“, *Зборник радова Византолошког института* 7 (1961), 8; Ћук, *Србија и Венеција*, 39. f. 69; Порчић, Исаиловић, „Западна политика“, 174–175.

⁹ Ћук, *Србија и Венеција*, 41; Порчић, Исаиловић, „Западна политика“, 178–179.

¹⁰ Ћук, *Србија и Венеција*, 44–49.

freedom to travel and trade within his kingdom.¹¹ Despite efforts to improve relations, tensions between Serbia and Venice had not been entirely resolved. Many Venetian merchants demanded compensation for debts and losses they had incurred in the Serbian king's realm in previous years. As we shall see, numerous economic disputes that had troubled Serbia's relations with Venice under Dušan's predecessors continued to be a burden during his reign as well. In the following pages, we will examine how Stefan Dušan sought to address these issues and attempted to move Serbian-Venetian relations beyond their narrow economic framework. In other words, we will explore how he transformed the nature of these relations and, driven by his ambitions, sought to elevate them to a higher level.

Debts of Venetian Merchants and the Kotor Agreement

During the conflict between Stefan Dečanski and Stefan Dušan, many Dubrovnik merchants suffered losses, as did Venetian traders, who had already been affected in previous years.¹² As soon as Dušan ascended the throne, the Venetian government pressed for the repayment of debts owed to its citizens by the people of Kotor. Although this issue had been raised during Dečanski's reign, it became a major political problem under Dušan, facing strong resistance from the citizens of Kotor.¹³

A portion of Serbia's urban population, particularly the people of Kotor, were indebted to Venetian creditors.¹⁴ Numerous documents and diplomatic disputes from the early years of Dušan's reign attest to the role of Venetian merchants as lenders to the Serbian population. Throughout the spring of 1332, letters and envoys were exchanged between the Serbian king, the Municipality of Kotor, and the Venetian government. The Venetians had banned their merchants from traveling

¹¹ Катарина Митровић, „Писмо краља Стефана Уроша III млетачком дужду Франческу Дандолу“, *Стари српски архив* 15 (2016), 9–17; Небојша Порчић, Невен Исаиловић, *Документи владара средњовековне Србије и Босне у венецијанским збиркама* (Београд: Архив Србије, 2019), 27–29, 222–224.

¹² Ћук, *Србија и Венеција*, 52 f. 5.

¹³ *Ibid.*, 51.

¹⁴ About Kotor's debt to Venetians, see Ћук, *Србија и Венеција*, 140–162.

to Kotor in May of the previous year, and this ban remained in effect.¹⁵ However, in May 1332, the Senate passed a new resolution allowing Venetian merchants or their agents to travel to Kotor until the end of August to collect debts.¹⁶

Soon after, the people of Kotor changed their stance. Recognising the potential threat posed by their citizens' failure to repay Venetian debts, they ordered their judges in early July 1332 to rule in favour of debt repayment, regardless of local statutes.¹⁷ A month later, in a lawsuit between a Kotor citizen and a Venetian, the municipal judges ruled in favour of the Venetian, explicitly stating that the council and municipality had mandated the debt's settlement.¹⁸

Despite previous efforts, the people of Kotor continued to borrow from Venetian merchants, many of whom conducted business and resided temporarily or permanently in Kotor and Dubrovnik. As a result, unpaid debts kept accumulating, exacerbating tensions between Venice and Kotor and, by extension, Serbia. In the years that followed, Venetian authorities restricted travel to Kotor, granting permission only to certain merchants or their agents who had large sums of money to collect.¹⁹ Beyond outstanding debts, another major issue was the financial losses suffered by Venetian merchants, both in coastal regions and in the Serbian interior. One such case was that of the Venetian merchant Nicola Quirino, who suffered losses amounting to four thousand hyperpyra. In

¹⁵ *Ibid*, 51. The Venetians were particularly determined to seek compensation for the damages suffered by Nicolao Briuosso before the spring of 1332. During the rebellion of the Zetan noblemen, he had been intercepted and plundered by the nobleman Demetrius Suma. The Venetians appealed to the Serbian king in writing, requesting his assistance. On 10 June 1332 or 1333, Dušan responded to a letter from Doge Francesco Dandolo, promising that the losses would be compensated as soon as Demetrius Suma was captured. However, it seems that this promise was never fulfilled, and the matter remained unresolved. Катарина Митровић, Милица Кисић Божић, „Писмо краља Стефана Душана млетачком дужду Франческу Дандолу“, *Стари српски архив* 16 (2017), 9–18; Порчић, Исаиловић, *Документи владара*, 29–30, 224–226.

¹⁶ Ћук, *Србија и Венеција*, 51.

¹⁷ *Историја Црне Горе, књ II: Од краја XII до краја XV вијека, том I: Црна Гора у доба Немањића* (Титоград: Редакција за историју Црне Горе, 1970), 44; Ћук, *Србија и Венеција*, 52.

¹⁸ Ћук, *Србија и Венеција*, 52.

¹⁹ *Ibid*, 52.

October 1333, he received partial compensation, with the remaining amount being paid off in the following years.²⁰

As this situation illustrates, the position of Venetian—and also Dubrovnik—merchants in Serbia had become increasingly precarious. Consequently, fewer and fewer of them traveled to Kotor, negatively impacting the city's trade and economy. At the same time, the Venetian government intensified its pressure regarding unpaid debts and damages, forcing both the Serbian king and the people of Kotor to make concessions. The outcome was the conclusion of an agreement between Kotor and Venice, which Dušan later extended on two further occasions. The treaty was signed on 30 December 1335 in Venice. It was ratified on behalf of the Venetian commune by its provisors, while the Kotor commune was represented by the king's delegate, Marin Filipov. The Serbian king acted solely as the supreme guarantor.²¹ The agreement protected only the rights of the Venetians in Kotor, while the rights of the people of Kotor in Venice were not even mentioned. The Venetians effectively dictated the terms, making debt collection easier while simultaneously nullifying customary practices that had previously protected debtors. The presence and operations of Venetian merchants were so crucial to Kotor that its inhabitants were forced to accept conditions that directly contradicted the provisions of their city's statute.²²

The terms of the agreement were unfavourable to the people of Kotor, and as a result, they did not always adhere to them. In early 1338, the Venetians reminded them that they were bound by the treaty with Venice and that invoking the authority of the Serbian king was not a valid justification. They demanded that Kotor's authorities ensure the return of property to the wronged Venetian merchants. If they failed to do so, Venice warned that it would take matters into its own hands to protect its subjects from such blatant injustice.²³

²⁰ *Ibid.*, 52. f. 5.

²¹ *Ibid.*, 53.

²² *Историја Црне Горе II/1*, 43. More about this treaty see Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 53–54. f. 9; Марица Маловић-Ђукић, „Котор у XIII и XIV веку“ (докторска дисертација, Универзитет у Београду, 1987), 51–52; Sime Ljubić, *Listine o одноšajih između južnoga Slavenstva i Mletačke republike, knjiga I* (Zagreb: JAZU, 1868), 464–466.

²³ Sime Ljubić, *Listine o одноšajih između južnoga Slavenstva i Mletačke republike, knjiga II* (Zagreb: JAZU, 1870.), 15–16; Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 54; Маловић-Ђукић, *Котор у XIII и XIV веку*, 53.

Later, at the request of Doge Andrea Dandolo, Stefan Dušan extended the Venetian-Kotor agreement on two occasions. The first extension, issued on 15 October 1345, prolonged the treaty for two years, with the note: "for this period and as long as it pleases both Kotor and you."²⁴ Dušan informed the people of Kotor that Venetian merchants were permitted to collect their debts not only in Kotor but throughout his entire kingdom. Two and a half years later, on 1 April 1348, Emperor Dušan extended the treaty for an additional eight years. He informed the doge that he had instructed the people of Kotor to abide by the agreement but also requested that they not be subjected to undue difficulties at the hands of the Venetians without proper legal proceedings. This was the first instance in which Dušan intervened to advocate for certain rights of Kotor's citizens.²⁵

In addition to the people of Kotor, Dušan himself was indebted to Venetian merchants. On multiple occasions, the Serbian ruler confiscated goods from merchants to meet urgent needs. It is known that he did so in 1332, during his wedding, and likely again in 1335 at fairs in Gračanica, Polog, and Prizren, where he seized textiles and wine from Dubrovnik traders. Given that Venetian merchants often acted as creditors to Dubrovnik traders, it is possible that the confiscated goods belonged to the Venetians.²⁶ For years, both the Venetians and the people of Dubrovnik sought to recover their claims from the Serbian emperor. While Dušan never denied these debts, he repeatedly delayed their repayment, creating difficulties for the merchants. To settle these obligations, the Serbian ruler occasionally granted Venetian merchants full or partial revenues from the Saint Demetrius income (*Svetodmitarski dohodak*).²⁷

Debt collection was not the only difficulty the Venetians faced in the Serbian state. They frequently complained about acts of violence and robbery committed against their merchants. Additionally, they were troubled by newly imposed levies, primarily the introduction and collection of

²⁴ Катарина Митровић, Милица Кисић Божић, „Писмо краља Стефана Душана млетачком дужду Андреи Дандолу“, *Стари српски архив 18* (2019), 9–24.; Порчић, Исаиловић, *Документи владара*, 31–33, 228–230.

²⁵ Ћук, *Србија и Венеција*, 54–55.

²⁶ *Ibid*, 70.

²⁷ *Ibid*, 70.

new customs duties. In response, on 31 March 1349, the Venetian government decided to send a diplomatic mission to Serbia regarding the burden of these new levies and compensation for the damages suffered by "our faithful subjects from Dubrovnik, who have endured and continue to endure losses in the kingdom of Raška."²⁸ It was also decided to address a letter to Emperor Dušan's protovestiaros, Nikola Buća, who was responsible for these damages and new taxes. Along with two other Dubrovnik citizens, Buća had been leasing Serbian customs revenues in 1348–1349, and it is likely that the three of them had arbitrarily charged traders higher duties than usual, prompting complaints from both Venetian and Dubrovnik merchants.²⁹

A week later, the Venetian Senate discussed instructions for the envoy to Serbia. Among his many tasks, one of the key objectives was to secure compensation for the damages suffered by Venetian and Dubrovnik merchants. By the end of April 1349, Marquess Niccolò Giorgio was appointed as the envoy.³⁰ He spent the summer at the Serbian court, but his mission only achieved success on 20 September 1349. On that day, a meeting and negotiations took place in Novo Brdo between Giorgi, Emperor Dušan, and three Dubrovnik envoys. The outcome of these negotiations was a set of three documents issued by Emperor Dušan.³¹

The first document provided a final reckoning of all outstanding debts, including those of the emperor, the empress, and the nobility. The total debt was estimated at over nine thousand hyperpyra, and the emperor pledged to repay it over the next three years. It is likely that this sum also included the previously mentioned debts owed to Venetian and Dubrovnik merchants.³² The second document, issued "for the sake

²⁸ *Ibid*, 71.

²⁹ *Ibid*, 72.

³⁰ *Ibid*, 72.

³¹ *Ibid*, 72; *Историја српског народа I*, 548. Niccolò Giorgi was the Marquess of Bodonitsa, located on the Aegean coast of central Greece. Following Dušan's conquest of Epirus and Thessaly in 1347/8, he became a direct neighbour of the Serbian state, Небојша Порчић, *Документи српских средњовековних владара у дубровачким збиркама: доба Немањића* (Београд: Балканолошки институт САНУ, 2017), 58.

³² Дејан Јечменица, „Хрисовуља цара Стефана Душана Дубровчанима са два пратећа акта“, *Стари српски архив 11* (2012), 48–50; Порчић, *Документи*, 58–61, 249–255; Ћук, *Србија и Венеција*, 72.

of my brother, the doge, and the Venetian envoy [...] of the city of Dubrovnik and at the request of their envoys," abolished the Trebinje customs duty, which had been among the newly introduced levies that the Venetians and Dubrovnik merchants had protested against.³³ Finally, the most significant document was a chrysobull issued by Emperor Dušan to the people of Dubrovnik, granting them the right to trade freely throughout Serbia and with all neighbouring lands. Additionally, the chrysobull prohibited the confiscation of goods from wrecked Venetian and Dubrovnik ships. The document also regulated several other matters of varying importance and was recorded in three copies—one for the emperor, one for the people of Dubrovnik, and one for the Venetians.³⁴

At the end of 1353 or early 1354, an intriguing incident occurred that not only reflected the state of Serbian-Venetian relations but also shed light on the internal dynamics within the Serbian ruling family. On two occasions, Emperor Dušan promised that he would not seize goods from Venetian ships. However, his viceroy in the regions of Kanina and Valona, despot John Komnenos Asen, who was also the brother of Empress Helena, did not adhere to this agreement. Near Valona, a Venetian vessel was looted. In response, the Venetians sent their envoy, Niccolò Giorgi, to negotiate with the despot. When John Komnenos Asen refused to return the stolen goods or compensate for the damages, Venice appealed to his suzerain, Emperor Dušan. The Serbian emperor informed the Venetians that, according to despot John, the looted goods did not belong to them but to other individuals. Moreover, the despot offered to send the goods to Venice for arbitration, though he ultimately failed to do so. Dušan was displeased with this situation, yet, as he stated, "out of love for the empress, he could say nothing more." Nonetheless, the Serbian ruler was willing to compensate for the damages by sending 1,120 hyperpyra via his envoy Mihailo Bučić, at a rate of 16 hyperpyra per libra. However, whether this compensation was ever paid remains unknown.³⁵

³³ Јечменица, „Хрисовуља цара Стефана Душана“, 46–47.

³⁴ *Ibid.*, 38–43; Nebojša Porčić, „The Right of Shipwreck in Medieval Serbia“, *Анали Правног факултета у Београду* 70/1 (2022), 12–13.

³⁵ Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 72–73; Бариша Крекић, „Млеци и унутрашњост Балкана у четрнаестом веку“, *Зборник радова Византолошког института* 21 (1982), 148.

At the beginning of 1354, the Venetian envoy Zanino Novello visited the Serbian court. In his report sent to Venice on 24 February, he stated that the Venetians had complained about robberies committed against their merchants operating in Serbia. Although Emperor Dušan had ordered Petar, son of protovestiarios Nikola Buća, to pay for the damages, he failed to do so. Zanino Novello also attempted to secure compensation for the considerable losses suffered by the Venetian merchant Polo Quirin, which had been inflicted by Luka Kimo of Ulcinj. However, the Venetian envoy was unsuccessful in this matter as well, concluding in frustration that "the costs are high, and nothing can be recovered."³⁶

In mid-1354, Venice dispatched another envoy to Emperor Dušan to discuss outstanding debts owed to Venetian creditors. These debts were owed not only by the Serbian ruler himself but also by his subjects, who had financial obligations to the Venetians. The envoy was sent "on behalf of our noblemen and other merchants who are in the lands of Raška and are owed large sums of money by the king or those regions".³⁷ However, it appears that, once again, all efforts to recover these claims remained fruitless.³⁸

Serbia and Venice in the Early Years of Dušan's Reign

Unlike his predecessors, Stefan Dušan pursued an overtly friendly policy towards Dubrovnik. This stance was likely influenced by his considerations regarding Venice, with which, despite the aforementioned difficulties, he sought to maintain good relations. Venice would later play a significant role in Dušan's broader strategic plans.³⁹ It appears that early in his reign, towards the end of 1331, King Stefan Dušan issued a charter granting Dubrovnik merchants the freedom to trade.⁴⁰ His amicable policy towards Dubrovnik is further demonstrated by the sale of the Ston region to the city in 1333. Through this transaction, the

³⁶ Пук, *Србија и Венеција*, 73; Крекић, „Млеци и унутрашњост Балкана“, 148.

³⁷ Пук, *Србија и Венеција*, 71; Крекић, „Млеци и унутрашњост Балкана“, 148.

³⁸ Пук, *Србија и Венеција*, 71.

³⁹ *Историја српског народа I*, 546.

⁴⁰ Дејан Јечменица, „Повеља краља Стефана Душана Дубровчанима о трговини“, *Стари српски архив 10* (2011), 17–27.

Republic of Venice—Dubrovnik’s suzerain—was also able to expand its territorial influence.⁴¹ However, what is surprising is that the Venetians seem to be absent from the negotiations between the Serbian king and the people of Dubrovnik.

More than any of his predecessors, Dušan procured large quantities of weapons from Venice. These purchases not only reflect Serbia’s good relations with Venice but also serve as evidence of Dušan’s expansionist ambitions. Records indicate that he acquired weapons in May 1336,⁴² following conflicts with Byzantium and Hungary. Further arms purchases, recorded twice in 1341⁴³ and once more the following year,⁴⁴ suggest that Dušan was preparing for an offensive against Byzantine territories.⁴⁵

In addition to acquiring weapons, Dušan also recruited mercenaries from the West through Venice. In early December 1336, the Venetians permitted 300 mercenaries traveling to Serbia to pass through their territory.⁴⁶ However, in May 1341, while offering their

⁴¹ More about this in: Дејан Јечменица, „Прва стонска повеља краља Стефана Душана“, *Стари српски архив* 9 (2010), 25–37; Дејан Јечменица, „Друга стонска повеља краља Стефана Душана“, *Стари српски архив* 9 (2010), 51–56; Синиша Мишић, „Стон и Пељешац од 1326. до 1333. године“, *Историјски часопис* 42–43 (1995–1996), 29–30. and Дејан Јечменица, „Стефан Душан и Дубровник“ (докторска дисертација, Универзитет у Београду, 2012), 136–168.

⁴² Ljubić, *Listine II*, 4. As early as June 1332, Dušan’s envoys were making purchases in Venice on behalf of the Serbian king, likely intended for his wedding (Ljubić, *Listine I*, 384). In May or June 1333, Dušan requested the authorities in Dubrovnik to hand over 8,000 hyperpyra—received from the sale of the Ston region—to their citizen Lampro Menčetić, whom he was sending to Venice to procure items necessary for our kingdom. The sources do not specify what Menčetić was supposed to purchase or whether the transaction was completed. However, considering that Dušan most frequently acquired weaponry in Venice and that he was likely preparing for a military campaign against Byzantium at the time—a campaign that indeed took place the following year—it is reasonable to assume that, on this occasion as well, Dušan was purchasing arms in Venice. Порчић, *Документи*, 52.

⁴³ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 111, 118.

⁴⁴ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 144.

⁴⁵ On the procurement of weapons from, or through, Venice, see Марко Алексић, „Реформа српске војске у време Стефана Душана“, *Војноисторијски гласник* 2 (2015), 16–19.

⁴⁶ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 11. Jireček was the first to assume that these mercenaries were from Germany., Константин Јиречек, *Историја Срба. Политичка историја до 1537. године, књига I*. Прев. Јован Радонић (Београд: Слово љубве, 1978), 111. The mercenaries were probably led by the knight Palman, and they probably came from the Habsburg lands,

apologies, the Venetians refused to allow the Serbian king to recruit troops in Venice itself.⁴⁷

Dušan's efforts to maintain good relations with Venice are also reflected in a letter written either in 1341 or sometime between 1333 and 1339. The letter reveals that a ship—or possibly multiple ships—was shipwrecked along a coastline under the Serbian king's rule. Although custom dictated that all goods from a shipwrecked vessel belonged to the ruler of the land where the wreck occurred, King Dušan agreed to compensate the Venetian passengers and merchants. He even requested that the doge send trusted envoys to assist in assessing the damages.⁴⁸

Perhaps the clearest evidence of the good relations between Serbia and Venice is a letter delivered to the Venetian government in early June 1340 by Dušan's envoys. The letter contained various requests and proposals. Above all, the Serbian king sought assurance that he and his family would be granted refuge in Venice in the event of any misfortune.⁴⁹ In return, he offered military assistance in times of war, promising a contingent of 500 cavalry. Moreover, he was personally willing to lead these troops "even into the regions of Lombardy".⁵⁰

What was likely of greatest interest to the Venetians was Dušan's guarantee of free passage for Venetian merchants through his lands. He emphasised that "the passage through our territories could be fruitful and beneficial for our kingdom," particularly for traders transporting goods to Constantinople and the Byzantine Empire. Additionally, the Serbian king assured Venetian merchants that he would compensate any losses they might incur while conducting business in Serbia.⁵¹

Aleksandar Uzelać, „Palman of Letinberch and his Teutonic Company“, *Историјски часопис* 72 (2023), 149–150.

⁴⁷ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 111.

⁴⁸ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 111–112; Катарина Митровић, Милица Кисић Божић, „Писмо краља Стефана Душана млетачком дужду Франческу Дандолу“, *Стари српски архив* 17 (2018), 9–20; Порчић, Исаиловић, *Документи владара*, 30, 226–228.

⁴⁹ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 75; Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 55. It appears that at that time, due to illness, Dušan was in a difficult position. The cessation of warfare following the peace agreement with Byzantium in 1336 had significantly weakened his political standing, Смиља Марјановић-Душанић, *Владарска идеологија Немањића* (Београд: СЛИО, 1997), 171.

⁵⁰ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 75–76; Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 55–56; Момчило Спремић, *Србија и Венеција (VI–XVI век)* (Београд: Службени гласник, 2014), 37.

⁵¹ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 76; Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 56.

Finally, Dušan requested that Venice provide galleys for transporting his delegation to the Holy Land. Sometime between 1337 and 1339, Dušan had suffered from a severe illness, one so grave that, as he himself stated in his letter to Venice, "his physicians despaired, losing hope for his recovery." At that time, the Serbian ruler vowed that if he were spared from the grip of this affliction, he would build a church and monastery in Jerusalem in honour of the Saviour. Since he had recovered, he now sought to fulfil this vow by sending several of his noblemen, along with a large sum of money, to Jerusalem via Cyprus. For this mission, he requested two galleys from Venice, offering to arm them at his own expense.⁵²

Doge Bartolomeo Gradenigo and the Venetian senators received Dušan's offers and proposals with great satisfaction. They expressed their gratitude for his military assistance and decided to grant Venetian citizenship to the Serbian emperor and his family.⁵³ This was promptly formalised—on 12 June 1340, Dušan, along with his family, was officially named a Venetian citizen by a chrysobull sealed with gold.⁵⁴ Furthermore, the Venetians assured Dušan that Venice's borders would always remain open to him. At the same time, they urged him to ensure that Venetian merchants passing through his kingdom were treated safely, freely, and favourably.⁵⁵

Venice also responded positively to Dušan's final request. However, citing the papal ban on trade with Egypt, they explained that Venetian ships no longer sailed directly to Jerusalem.⁵⁶ Instead, they

⁵² Ljubić, *Listine II*, 76; Ћук, *Србија и Венеција*, 56; Божидар Ферјанчић, Сима Ћирковић, *Стефан Душан, краљ и цар 1331–1355*. (Београд: Завод за уџбенике и наставна средства, 2005), 322.

⁵³ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 76–77; Ћук, *Србија и Венеција*, 56; Спремић, *Србија и Венеција*, 37.

⁵⁴ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 78–79.

⁵⁵ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 76–77; Ћук, *Србија и Венеција*, 56.

⁵⁶ After the fall of Acre in 1291, Pope Nicholas IV issued a bull prohibiting trade with Egypt and the *partes infidelium*. These restrictions severely affected the states that had benefited from such trade, including Venice. In an effort to curb smuggling, which had spread following the papal decree, the Venetians reinforced the ban on trading with "non-believers" for all their subjects during the second decade of the 14th century and then again in 1323, Бариша Крекић, *Дубровник и Левант (1280–1460)* (Београд: Научно дело, 1956), 101–102). It should be noted that while the papal bull forbade trade, it did not prohibit the dispatch of embassies or any other form of communication with Egypt.

could offer passage for his envoys only as far as Cyprus. They proposed that Dušan's men embark in August on one of the six galleys that would be sailing to Cyprus at that time, pointing out that this option would be more cost-effective than arming two galleys himself. Should he reject this proposal, they suggested that he outfit two galleys somewhere along the Dalmatian coast, provided that they did not sail beyond Cyprus. Additionally, for greater security, these ships could join the Venetian fleet.⁵⁷

It appears that during the Nemanjić era, Serbian diplomatic missions always chartered galleys from other states when travelling by sea and that they always set out from Dubrovnik.⁵⁸ Thus, Dušan's appeal to Venice for the transport of his envoys should come as no surprise. Although the Serbian emperor likely had ships within his kingdom capable of ensuring his envoys' passage to the Holy Land, he may have considered that travelling under the banner of St Mark would provide his men with greater security.

Dušan's letter was, in a sense, a prelude to future cooperation. Judging by subsequent events, his primary motive for drawing closer to Venice was the hope that the Venetians would one day assist him in conquering Constantinople. However, the question arises as to whether the Serbian king had already begun laying the groundwork for this ambition at this time. If so, he was not yet revealing his plans.

However, it is important to keep in mind that the Venetians, as traders, officially traveled only as far as Cyprus, venturing beyond that point only if they dared to smuggle goods. Unfortunately, we do not know how far Venetian galleys actually transported Dušan's delegation or whether they transported them at all. If the Venetians had indeed only taken the Serbian envoys as far as Cyprus, the delegation would surely have found a way to continue their journey from Cyprus to the Holy Land. On the other hand, it is noteworthy that four years later, Dušan sent an embassy to the Sultan of Egypt (Александар Узелац, „Србија и мамелучки Египат током XIII и XIV века“, *Београдски историјски гласник IV* (2013), 31–32). Given the aforementioned circumstances, it should not be ruled out that, as in the previous instance—if that was indeed the case—the Venetian galleys may have once again transported the Serbian delegation to Cyprus, from where they continued on other ships, possibly even Egyptian ones, to reach their final destination in Egypt.

⁵⁷ Ферјанчић, Ђирковић, *Стефан Душан*, 322; Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 56.

⁵⁸ More about this: Nebojša Porčić, „Information on Travel of Nemanjić Embassies: Content and Context“, *Balkanica* 47 (2016), 106–107.

For the Venetians, on the other hand, it was an easy decision to respond positively to Dušan's proposals. Granting citizenship had always been a means by which Venice, to varying degrees, secured the loyalty of potential allies. Providing two galleys for Dušan's envoys was a service that came at virtually no cost to Venice, as the Serbian king was willing to equip them himself. Meanwhile, Dušan's offer of military assistance—which he would extend to Venice again in later years—was of little value to the republic, at least at that moment. As already noted, as a maritime trading power, Venice and its merchants were far more interested in Dušan's guarantee of free passage through his lands, as well as his promise that any damages they suffered would be duly compensated.

Venetians in Serbian-Byzantine relations

In the summer of 1342, the Serbian king allied with the Byzantine pretender, John Kantakouzenos, and directed against the legitimate government in Constantinople. Military operations soon commenced, and throughout that year and the next, the imperial authorities sent envoys to the Serbian king in an attempt to break the alliance.⁵⁹ However, when their efforts proved unsuccessful, they turned to Venice, hoping that it might succeed where they had failed. Accepting their request, the Venetians decided on May 12, 1343, to send an envoy to the Serbian king. Marin Venier was selected for this mission, with the primary task of facilitating reconciliation between Dušan and the imperial government. He likely set out only in mid-June,⁶⁰ but an unforeseen mishap forced him to return to Venice. The Senate revisited the matter on June 19, and resolved that the Venetian envoy should depart for Serbia without delay, "since it has already been publicly announced in our city of Venice and elsewhere that we are sending an envoy to the said king in service of the empire". Marin Venier spent almost the entire summer in

⁵⁹ For more details on Serbian-Byzantine relations in 1342/3, see *Историја српског народа I*, 516–520.

⁶⁰ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 174–175; Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 57; Ферјанчић, Ђирковић, *Стефан Душан*, 129. The Byzantines also asked the Venetians for help in the fight against the Turks, Ljubić, *Listine II*, 174. At the beginning of June, Marin Venier received some additional duties, including working with the Serbian king on the issue of the debts of Venetian merchants, Ljubić, *Listine II*, 175.

Serbia and likely sent a report to Venice in August, informing them that peace had been concluded between the Serbian king and the government in Constantinople.⁶¹ In early September, the Venetian Senate decided that Venier should return to Venice, as he had completed his mission. At the same time, it was also decided that congratulations should be sent to the Serbian king on the engagement of his son to the Byzantine emperor's sister.⁶² Although the Venetian envoy's mission undoubtedly contributed to the agreement between the Serbian king and the imperial government, the most decisive factor influencing these events was the rupture between Dušan and John Kantakouzenos in April 1343, when the latter abandoned their joint camp and launched a campaign to capture Veroia.⁶³

In the autumn of 1345, a significant phase of Dušan's conquests in Byzantine territories came to an end, culminating in the capture of Serres on September 25, 1345.⁶⁴ By mid-October, the Serbian king wrote to the Venetian doge, declaring that he had become the ruler of almost the entire Byzantine Empire.⁶⁵ Between November 1345 and January 1346 (most likely on Christmas Day 1345), Dušan proclaimed himself emperor.⁶⁶

⁶¹ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 178–179; Тук, *Србија и Венеција*, 57.

⁶² Ljubić, *Listine II*, 192; Тук, *Србија и Венеција*, 57; Ферјанчић, Ђирковић, *Стефан Душан*, 129; Radivoj Radić, „Venezia, Bisanzio e la Serbia attorno ala metà del XIV secolo“, *Глас CDIV Српске академије наука и уметности, Одељење историјских наука*, књ. 13 (2006), 97.

⁶³ *Историја српског народа I*, 520–521. The agreement between Dušan and the Constantinopolitan government was undoubtedly beneficial for Venice as well. The cessation of military threats, at least for the time being, was crucial for Venetian merchants, as they could only trade freely in times of peace. Additionally, Venetian traders faced problems with Turkish pirates, which is why, during this period, Venice repeatedly entered into various anti-Turkish alliances alongside Byzantium and several other states. In order to protect its merchants effectively, Venice needed a strong government in Constantinople—one that would not be preoccupied with civil wars but rather focused on combating the Turks. For more details on this, see extensive discussions in Donald M. Nicol, *Byzantium and Venice, A Study in Diplomatic and Cultural relations* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1988), 246–263.

⁶⁴ *Историја српског народа I*, 523.

⁶⁵ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 278. This is the same letter in which Dušan grants permission for the extension of the agreement between the Venetians and the people of Kotor for two years and in which he also offers assistance to the Venetians against Zadar.

⁶⁶ Ферјанчић, Ђирковић, *Стефан Душан*, 151.

In January 1346, Dušan's envoys visited Venice, informing the Venetians of his intention to be crowned emperor and proposing an alliance for a joint attack on Byzantium and the conquest of Constantinople.⁶⁷ Two months later, Venice sent its response. While the Venetians welcomed his plan to assume the imperial title and extended their heartfelt congratulations, they refused to join his proposed alliance against Byzantium. They justified their decision by citing their ongoing war with Zadar, as well as their existing treaties with Byzantium, which they had sworn to uphold.⁶⁸

The destruction of the Byzantine Empire was not in Venice's interest. Although the republic had previously joined anti-Byzantine alliances on two occasions within the past seventy years, in both cases, Byzantium would not have been replaced by a strong new state. Indeed, as is well known, Venice had built its commercial empire upon the ruins of Byzantium. However, this time, should the Serbian emperor succeed in taking Constantinople, Byzantium would be replaced by a powerful state—one certainly stronger than the weakened Byzantine Empire of the time—something that was not in Venice's favour.⁶⁹

From the Venetian perspective, Dušan's assumption of the imperial title did not represent any significant change. The title of emperor had long since begun to lose its prestige, with multiple claimants, including the Byzantine emperor, the Holy Roman Emperor, the Bulgarian ruler, the titular emperors of the Latin Empire, and now the Serbian king. Venice had no difficulty addressing the rulers of all these states as emperors. Even the Venetian doges referred to themselves as "Lords of a Quarter and a Half of the Roman Empire". Perhaps this best illustrates just how little importance Venice placed on imperial titulature.⁷⁰

⁶⁷ Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 59.

⁶⁸ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 326; Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 59–60.

⁶⁹ Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 60.

⁷⁰ M. Dinić had already observed that around this time, more precisely in the 1350s, the Venetian doge's title "Lord of a Quarter and a Half of the Roman Empire" fell out of use. Although the cessation of its usage coincides with the proclamation of the Serbian Empire, the two events are not causally linked, Михаило Динић, „Душанова царска титула у очима савременика“, у *Зборник у част шесте стогодишњице Законика цара Душана I*, ур. Никола Радојчић (Београд: САН, 1951), 112. The change likely occurred after the Treaty of Zadar in 1358, when the Hungarians forced the Venetian

As seen earlier, in March 1346, the Venetians acknowledged Dušan's intention to be crowned emperor and sent him their warmest congratulations. Yet, paradoxically, in the very decree instructing that Dušan be congratulated, he was referred to as king.⁷¹ Venice did not send an official delegation to his coronation, which took place in Skopje on April 16, 1346.⁷²

It can be said that Venice maintained a certain indifference regarding the question of Dušan's imperial title. "They did not refuse to recognise the new emperor, but neither did they show particular enthusiasm in addressing him as such".⁷³ In later references to Serbia in Venetian sources during the reigns of Dušan and his son Uroš, the Venetians alternated between referring to Serbian rulers as either emperor or king, and sometimes even used both titles simultaneously (*imperator et rex Sclavoniae*). Simply put, it made little difference to them how the Serbian ruler was titled, leading to instances where both titles appeared interchangeably within the same document. However, when officially addressing Dušan, the Venetian government was careful to refer to him as emperor.⁷⁴ For example, when Doge Andrea Dandolo issued a diploma granting Venetian nobility to Dušan on May 25, 1350, he referred to him as *serenissimus dominus Stephanus, Grecorum imperator semper augustus et Raxie rex illustris* ("The Most Serene Lord Stefan, Emperor of the Greeks, Ever August, and Illustrious King of Raška").⁷⁵ Finally, it can be assumed that Venetians who had commercial ties with Serbia or had personal contact with the Serbian ruler to some extent adopted the Serbian perspective on Dušan's imperial title. For instance, Zanino Novello, a former Venetian envoy to Serbia, referred to the Serbian ruler in his report as *imperator de Sclavonia*.⁷⁶

doge to remove Croatia and Dalmatia from his titlature, after which it was simply styled *dux Venetiarum et cetera* (Vittorio Lazzarini, „I titoli dei dogi di Venezia“, *Nuovo Archivio Veneto*, nuova serie – anno 2 V/II (1903) 300–301).

⁷¹ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 326.

⁷² Динић, „Душанова царска титула“, 111.

⁷³ *Ibid*, 111.

⁷⁴ *Ibid*, 111–112.

⁷⁵ *Ibid*, 112; Ljubić, *Listine III*, 185.

⁷⁶ Ljubić, *Listine III*, 263.

Until the end of his life, Emperor Dušan remained committed to his ultimate political objective—the conquest of Constantinople. Although the Venetians were unwilling to assist him in this endeavour, Dušan continued to believe that he could eventually secure their support. In the meantime, he focused on expanding his empire by conquering additional Byzantine territories. A major step in this direction was his capture of Epirus in 1347, followed by Thessaly in 1348.⁷⁷ With these conquests, the Serbian Empire became a direct neighbour of Venetian possessions along the Aegean coast. By 3 January 1349, the Venetians congratulated Dušan *de prosperitatibus suis* (on his successes),⁷⁸ while simultaneously recommending to him “our fortress of Phthleion and our other lands and loyal subjects”.⁷⁹ Although Dušan did not adopt the title Count of Vlachia after these conquests, the Venetians referred to him as *imperatore di Rascia, despoto di Romania e di Arta, conte di Vlachia* when his envoy visited Venice in 1350. The title Count of Vlachia was most likely added by the Venetians themselves, perhaps as a way to emphasise the Serbian emperor’s recent achievements.⁸⁰ As is often the case, even among neighbouring states with good relations, occasional disputes arose. For instance, in early 1350, the inhabitants of Phthleion suffered damages caused by Catalans and Albanians under the command of Dušan’s governor in Thessaly, Preljub.⁸¹

Despite these tensions, Dušan continued to place great hopes in a potential alliance with Venice. Out of consideration for them, he sought reconciliation with the Bosnian ban and continued to purchase weapons from Venice. Records from 1348–1349 indicate that Dušan even acquired ships, fully armed for defensive purposes.⁸²

⁷⁷ Ферјанчић, Ђирковић, Стефан Душан, 185–189.

⁷⁸ Sime Ljubić, *Listine o jednošajih između južnoga Slavenstva i Mletačke republike, knjiga III* (Zagreb: JAZU, 1872), 110; Божидар Ферјанчић, *Тесалија у XIII и XIV веку* (Београд: Византолошки институт САНУ, 1974), 229.

⁷⁹ Ljubić, *Listine III*, 110; Ферјанчић, *Тесалија у XIII и XIV веку*, 229; Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 68.

⁸⁰ Ферјанчић, *Тесалија у XIII и XIV веку*, 229.

⁸¹ *Ibid.*, 230; Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 68.

⁸² Dušan initially purchased three ships, and later the Venetians allowed the Serbian emperor to acquire one more, while at the same time rejecting his request to arm it in Venice, Ljubić, *Listine III*, 75, 109, 133–134. In June 1349, the Venetians permitted Dušan

In the spring of 1350, Dušan sent a long letter to the Venetian doge through his envoy, Mihailo Buća. In it, he proposed cooperation on various issues and requested Venetian assistance. Among other things, he sought Venetian citizenship and nobility for himself and his family, protection and asylum, mutual military aid, unrestricted trade, and the abolition of all tariffs. Most importantly, however, he once again asked for Venetian support in his conquest of Constantinople. In the letter, Dušan claimed to already control ten out of twelve parts of Byzantine territory, with the exception of Constantinople. He stated his intention to capture the city but emphasised that this would be impossible without Venetian support and their fleet. If Venice agreed to his proposal, the Serbian emperor was willing to cede Epirus to them or, after taking the Byzantine capital, to grant them Pera, the district of Constantinople controlled by the Genoese.⁸³

The Venetians responded positively to Dušan's request for citizenship, granting it to him and his family at the end of May 1350. Dušan, his wife Helena, his son Uroš, and their heirs were admitted *in cives Veneciarum, ac si oriundi forent*, meaning they were also granted Venetian nobility.⁸⁴ The republic also accepted his proposals for mutual cooperation but refused to support his planned attack on Constantinople.⁸⁵ Venice justified its decision by stating that it was *in treugua cum*

to procure 100 shields *more Sclavorum* ("in the Slavic manner"), 100 breastplates, and 100 chainmail gloves. Ljubić, *Listine III*, 134.

⁸³ Ljubić, *Listine III*, 174–176; Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 69; Ферјанчић, Ђирковић, *Стефан Душан*, 192.

⁸⁴ Ljubić, *Listine III*, 185. It should be noted that Dušan had already been granted Venetian citizenship in 1340. Later, John Kantakouzenos reproached him for becoming a Venetian citizen, or rather, a nobleman. At the end of 1350, the two emperors held negotiations outside the walls of Thessalonica. "And at that meeting, when asked by the emperor why he had endured such disgrace as to enroll himself among the senators of Venice, despite holding greater power than any of them, he replied that it was out of fear of him and added that it was not at all surprising that he had yielded to it." *Византијски извори за историју народа Југославије VI*, ур. Фрањо Баришић и Божидар Ферјанчић (Београд: Византолошки институт САНУ, 1986), 535.

⁸⁵ Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 69. The good relations between the two states might also be reflected in the fact that in the summer of 1354, when Emperor Dušan sought closer ties with the Pope, his delegation to Avignon traveled through Venice. In mid-June, the Venetian Senate decided to send letters to Pope Innocent VI, recommending the Serbian envoys to him, Ферјанчић, Ђирковић, *Стефан Душан*, 298; Ljubić, *Listine III*, 264. Two

imperatore Constantinopolitano ("in a truce with the Emperor of Constantinople") and could not assist Dušan without committing a great offense against God „et violatione sacramenti nostri et derogatione honoris et fame nostre ("and violating our oath, and tarnishing our honour and reputation").⁸⁶ In early May, Venice once again wrote to Dušan, apologising for being unable to support him.⁸⁷

Earlier that year, envoys from John Kantakouzenos had visited Venice. At the time, Serbian forces were near Thessaloniki, effectively besieging the city. Kantakouzenos' envoys urged the Venetians to provide grain to the city's inhabitants, but Venice refused.⁸⁸ Although they sought to avoid involvement in the Serbian-Byzantine conflict, the Venetians also wished to avoid provoking the Serbian emperor.

Shortly before the situation in Thessaloniki was resolved in late summer 1350, war broke out between Venice and Genoa. Around this time, John Kantakouzenos met with the Venetian envoy Jacopo Bragadin, who invited him to join the war between the two Italian republics — naturally, on the side of Venice. Kantakouzenos declined, explaining that he was "entirely preoccupied with the King, who, taking advantage of the civil war among the Romans, has seized no small number of cities and a great deal of land." The Venetian envoy assured the Byzantine emperor that he would mediate to improve relations between Kantakouzenos and Stefan Dušan, arguing that as a member of the Venetian Senate, the Serbian emperor was obliged to obey the republic.⁸⁹ However, despite Dušan's status as a Venetian citizen and senator, the republic had no real influence over him, unlike its other subjects. Kantakouzenos was well aware that the envoy's promises were empty words and therefore rejected his proposal.⁹⁰

years earlier, a Serbian envoy in Venice had informed the Doge about the Serbian emperor's stance toward the Byzantine emperor and the Ottoman emir Orhan, Радивој Радић, „Србија у делу венецијанског историчара Ђан Ђакома Каролда“, *Новоназарски зборник* 27 (2003), 127. This suggests that the Serbian emperor was keen for the Republic of Venice to be aware of the relations between these rulers.

⁸⁶ Ljubić, *Listine III*, 177–178.

⁸⁷ Ljubić, *Listine III*, 181; Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 69.

⁸⁸ Ферјанчић, Ђирковић, *Стефан Душан*, 245.

⁸⁹ *Ibid.*, 247–248.

⁹⁰ *Ibid.*, 248.

In the end, Byzantium did enter the war on Venice's side, aligning itself with King Peter IV of Aragon, while Genoa secured the support of King Louis I of Hungary. Following a naval battle in the Bosphorus in 1352, Byzantium withdrew from the conflict, which nonetheless continued until 1355.⁹¹ Ultimately, despite the occasional strains in their relationship, Venice and Byzantium remained closely intertwined. They maintained strong cooperation, and Venice enjoyed extensive trade privileges within the weakened Byzantine Empire. Moreover, as previously mentioned, Dušan sought to replace a weak Byzantium with a stronger state—his empire. Given these circumstances, it is clear why Venice had no interest in supporting Dušan's ambitions to overthrow the Byzantine Empire.

Venetian mediation in the Serbian-Bosnian conflict

Around the same time that Dušan was offering military assistance to Venice in its conflict with Hungary (a topic to be discussed later), the Venetians had the opportunity to act as mediators in the Serbian-Bosnian dispute over Hum. As early as 1343, ban Stjepan II Kotromanić of Bosnia had sought closer ties with Venice, sending envoys to the republic. On that occasion, he proposed an alliance against Hungary, which would include Serbia, Bosnia, Venice, the Dalmatian cities, and Croatian noblemen. Initially, Venice was receptive to the idea, seeing it as a means to protect its possessions in Dalmatia. However, the republic insisted on remaining unnamed in the alliance and urged ban Stjepan II to take the lead in forming it. Ultimately, the alliance never materialised.⁹² A few years later, under favourable circumstances, Emperor Dušan deemed it the right moment to reclaim Hum.⁹³

In early September 1346, ban Stjepan II requested that the Venetians send an envoy to Serbia to mediate peace. Venice agreed and dispatched its envoy, the notary Nicolino, to Emperor Dušan.⁹⁴ The Serbian

⁹¹ More about this war in: Nicol, *Byzantium and Venice*, 271–276; John Julius Norwich, *A History of Venice* (London: Penguin UK, 2003), 169–179.

⁹² Marko Šunjić, *Bosna i Venecija (odnosi u XIV i XV st.)* (Sarajevo: HKD Napredak, 1996), 26; Сима Ђирковић, *Историја средњовековне босанске државе* (Београд: Српска књижевна задруга, 1964), 118.

⁹³ Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 61.

⁹⁴ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 408.

emperor stated that, out of respect for Venice, he was willing to live in peace and friendship with ban Stjepan II, but only on the condition that the ban return the lands he had previously seized. If there was any dispute over rightful ownership, Dušan was prepared to accept arbitration to determine his legitimate claim. He proposed this solution with confidence, as his rights were clear, and arbitration would allow him to recover the land without resorting to war. Anticipating that ban Stjepan II would reject such terms, Dušan also suggested a temporary truce of two to three years, with both sides committing to refrain from hostilities.⁹⁵ His willingness to compromise was likely influenced by his ongoing campaigns in Byzantine territories at the time.⁹⁶

The available sources do not provide further details on what transpired next. It is possible that a short-term truce was reached with Venetian mediation at the end of 1346, given that no reports of hostilities between Dušan and ban Stjepan II emerged over the next two years.⁹⁷ Dušan had to exercise restraint due to his military commitments in Byzantium, while ban Stjepan II benefited from the status quo, as it allowed him to retain control over the disputed areas.⁹⁸ However, mutual distrust remained, and both rulers continued to purchase weapons from Venice. Dušan even acquired four galleys, though these were intended for his war against Byzantium. Meanwhile, in early 1348, ban Stjepan II's *vojvoda* (duke), Grgur Gojslavić, purchased military equipment worth 100 ducats.⁹⁹

By the spring of 1349, the truce between Serbia and Bosnia was likely nearing its expiration. Seeking to extend it on the basis that both sides would retain the territories they currently held, ban Stjepan II once again turned to Venice for assistance in mediation. In early April, the Venetian Senate sent its envoy, Marquess Niccolò Giorgio, to Serbia.¹⁰⁰ His primary mission was to secure compensation for damages suffered by Dubrovnik and Venetian merchants and to attempt to reconcile

⁹⁵ Пук, *Србија и Венеција*, 61–62; Šunjić, *Bosna i Venecija*, 44.

⁹⁶ Пук, *Србија и Венеција*, 62.

⁹⁷ *Ibid*, 63.

⁹⁸ Šunjić, *Bosna i Venecija*, 44.

⁹⁹ *Ibid*, 44.

¹⁰⁰ Ljubić, *Listine III*, 119–120; Пук, *Србија и Венеција*, 62; Bogumil Hrabak, „Venecija i bosanska država“, *Истраживања* 12 (1989), 419.

Dušan with the Byzantine emperors. If these tasks did not interfere, he was also permitted to mediate between Dušan and ban Stjepan II.

No progress was made in the initial attempts at mediation, as by July of the same year, ban Stjepan II once again pleaded for Venetian intervention. He urged the Venetians to expedite their mediation efforts and even placed his territory under the republic's protection.¹⁰¹ Additionally, he informed Venice of his intention to construct a fortress in Hum, near the mouth of the Neretva River. Anticipating opposition from Emperor Dušan, he assured the Venetians that he had no doubts about his land forces but sought their support at sea should the construction be threatened.¹⁰² The Venetians, however, opposed the building of the fortress and advised ban Stjepan II to abandon the project, warning that constructing a stronghold on disputed land could complicate peace negotiations with the Serbian emperor. Moreover, Venice feared that such a fortress might one day pose a threat to its cities and possessions in Dalmatia. The republic attempted diplomatic intervention in Serbia through its envoys, but ban Stjepan II's stance made successful mediation impossible. By the end of 1349, the Bosnian army launched an offensive into Serbian coastal territories, capturing some settlements, devastating others, and plundering the emperor's subjects.¹⁰³

In April of the following year, Dušan's envoy, Mihailo Buća, reported that the Serbian emperor had shown goodwill toward ban Stjepan II out of respect for Venice, which had recommended him. However, the ban had repaid this goodwill with aggression, leading his forces in raids on Serbian territory and seizing several settlements. Earlier, for the sake of Venice, Dušan had refrained from responding in kind. However, he now urged the republic to warn Ban Stjepan II and compel him to return the occupied lands and compensate for damages. Otherwise, Dušan warned, he would no longer be able to restrain himself from responding with force.¹⁰⁴ The Venetians replied that they valued both

¹⁰¹ Šunjić, *Bosna i Venecija*, 45.

¹⁰² *Ibid*, 45.

¹⁰³ Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 62; Hrabak, „Venecija i bosanska država“, 420; Ђирковић, *Историја средњовековне босанске државе*, 119; *Историја српског народа I*, 549. The Ban's army then, with the help of the Hungarians, penetrated through Gacko and Rudin, all the way to Kotor, Šunjić, *Bosna i Venecija*, 45.

¹⁰⁴ Šunjić, *Bosna i Venecija*, 45; Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 63.

rulers equally and wished for peace and harmony between them, as well as the removal of anything that could harm their subjects. They promised to write to ban Stjepan II and attempt to persuade him to change his stance and reconcile with the Serbian emperor.¹⁰⁵

At this point, Dušan was seriously considering turning his military might against Bosnia. One indication of this is that in April 1350, he sought a meeting with the Venetian doge in Dubrovnik or the region between Dubrovnik and the Neretva to discuss "certain great and difficult matters".¹⁰⁶ However, the Venetians easily refused this proposal, as their laws prohibited the doge from leaving the city. At this critical moment, ban Stjepan II faced perhaps the greatest threat of his otherwise successful reign, yet he still refused to relinquish Hum.¹⁰⁷ Venice decided to make one final attempt at mediation, hoping to resolve the dispute peacefully. In the first half of July—likely with prior approval from both sides—the republic selected two envoys, Tomas Gradenico and Nicolaus Faletro, and dispatched them to Serbia and Bosnia.¹⁰⁸ Before proceeding with negotiations, they were to stop in Dubrovnik to gather information on the latest developments in Serbian-Bosnian relations. Expecting prolonged negotiations, Venice allocated funds for the envoys' expenses for an initial two-month stay, with the option of an extension.¹⁰⁹ The Venetian envoys spent almost the entire summer travelling between the two rulers in an attempt to mediate, but the prospects for success were slim. Eventually, they reported back to Venice that not only had they achieved nothing, but they no longer had any hope of doing so. They lamented that their mission had incurred great expense while bringing little benefit to the republic. In late September, the Venetian government informed them that they could decide whether to stay or return home. However, the envoys remained for some time, as on 6 October, Venice instructed them to extend their stay. The republic feared that Dušan might attack Ston, and they were ordered to remain as long as there was

¹⁰⁵ Ljubić, *Listine III*, 175–176; Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 63.

¹⁰⁶ *Историја српског народа I*, 549; Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 63. f. 58; Šunjić, *Bosna i Venecija*, 46; Spremiћ, *Србија и Венеција*, 40.

¹⁰⁷ *Историја српског народа I*, 549.

¹⁰⁸ Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 63; Šunjić, *Bosna i Venecija*, 46.

¹⁰⁹ Ljubić, *Listine III*, 189–190; Šunjić, *Bosna i Venecija*, 46.

any threat to Dubrovnik and Ston.¹¹⁰ Ultimately, all Venetian efforts to reconcile the two rulers were in vain. Mavro Orbini later wrote that, while Dušan was on campaign in Bosnia, the Venetian government and Dubrovnik sent formal envoys to negotiate with him and resolve disputes with ban Stjepan II.¹¹¹ However, there is no confirmation of this in contemporary sources, making it likely that the mission of Tomas Gradenico and Nicolaus Faletro was Venice's final attempt at mediation.

Although Hum was of secondary importance to Dušan compared to Byzantine territories, he also refrained from attacking ban Stjepan II out of consideration for Venice, hoping that the republic might support his campaign against Byzantium. However, when Venice definitively refused to assist him in early May 1350, Dušan no longer saw any reason to hold back.¹¹²

In October 1350, Dušan launched a military campaign against Bosnia. In addition to his land forces, he had a fleet of four new galleys, which the Venetians had allowed him to purchase two years earlier as a sign of goodwill.¹¹³ The Serbian emperor invaded and occupied Hum, then crossed the Neretva valley and advanced westward. By mid-October, the citizens of Trogir and Šibenik anticipated that Dušan might reach the Krka River and prepared diplomatic missions with gifts in case of his arrival. He also may have intended to visit and assist his sister, Jelena, widow of Mladen III Bribirski, who ruled Omiš, Klis, and Skradin on behalf of her young son. However, alarming news from Macedonia—where John VI Kantakouzenos had begun capturing several Serbian cities—forced Dušan to abandon his campaign. He left garrisons in Hum, but they proved insufficient to hold the newly conquered territories against Ban Stjepan II's counteroffensive.¹¹⁴

As evidenced by the events above, Venice made considerable efforts to prevent war between Serbia and Bosnia. One reason for this was that Venice viewed both Serbia and Bosnia as potential allies in its struggle against Hungary. As is known, some efforts toward this had

¹¹⁰ Ljubić, *Listine III*, 199; Тук, *Србија и Венеција*, 63–64. f. 60.

¹¹¹ Мавро Орбин, *Краљевство Словена* (Зрењанин: Sezam Book d.o.o., 2006), 39.

¹¹² Šunjić, *Bosna i Venecija*, 46; Тук, *Србија и Венеција*, 63. and f. 60.

¹¹³ Јиречек, *Историја Срба I*, 228.

¹¹⁴ *Историја српског народа I*, 549–550.

already been made in 1343. Later, ban Stjepan II secretly cooperated with Venice during the siege of Zadar, leading the city's residents to blame him for Hungary's defeat.¹¹⁵ Meanwhile, Serbia had a history of conflicts with Hungary, making Dušan a natural ally for Venice. However, some historians suggest that Venice sought to reconcile the two rulers primarily out of fear that Serbia might reclaim Hum. If that were to happen, Serbia would become the only state bordering Dubrovnik. Given Dubrovnik's great significance to Venice, the republic preferred to have two separate rulers in the hinterland rather than a single, powerful Serbian ruler who could exert significant pressure on the city.¹¹⁶

The most important reason for Venice's persistence in maintaining peace in the interior of the Balkans, however, was its commercial interests. It is well known that the Venetians, primarily through Dubrovnik and Kotor merchants, exported numerous goods from Serbia and Bosnia—most notably, mining products. Venetian merchants and craftsmen frequently resided and conducted business in these territories. Furthermore, it is crucial to consider that, at this time, their commercial interests in the East were increasingly threatened, forcing them to shift their focus toward the interior of the Balkan Peninsula.¹¹⁷

Stefan Dušan and the Venetian-Hungarian conflict

Until now, the relations between Venice and Serbia have primarily portrayed the Venetians as mediators, negotiators, and envoys. However, two episodes from Venetian-Hungarian relations provided Stefan Dušan with an opportunity to assume a role typically associated with Venice, while the Venetians themselves became active participants in political developments.

In 1344, following the death of the Croatian nobleman Nelipac, the Hungarian king, Louis I, sought to take advantage of the situation

¹¹⁵ The Ban's envoy, who was in Venice in September 1346, proposed an alliance with the Venetians against King Louis and requested the royal city of Knin for the Ban. Regarding the actions of Ban Stjepan II Kotromanić during the siege of Zadar, see Ђирковић, *Историја средњовековне босанске државе*, 114–117.

¹¹⁶ Hrabak, „Venecija i bosanska država“, 421.

¹¹⁷ Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 64.

and seize his cities. At the same time, Venice, once a fierce adversary of Nelipac, transformed into the protector of his widow and young son. In July 1345, King Louis stayed near Bihać, where he received Knin and several other cities from Velislava, the late Nelipac's wife. This success attracted the allegiance of the most influential Croatian nobles, leaving the Dalmatian cities without a protective buffer. Consequently, they decided to send delegations to the Hungarian king to pledge their allegiance.¹¹⁸

Zadar, which until then had acknowledged Venetian sovereignty, followed suit. Three envoys were chosen to travel to the Hungarian king, present him with rich gifts, and secretly petition him to liberate their city from Venetian rule and accept it under his protection. However, by the time the envoys reached Bihać, Louis I had already departed. Nonetheless, the Venetians learned of Zadar's attempt to return to Hungarian control and decided to retaliate. At the beginning of August, they resolved to assemble an army to attack Zadar, declaring all its inhabitants enemies of the state and rebels.¹¹⁹ Meanwhile, in mid-August, the citizens of Zadar dispatched another embassy to King Louis, pleading for his protection. As the siege intensified, the Venetians began constructing a wooden fortress, known as the *bastida*, in mid-September to block access to the city from the mainland.¹²⁰

In October 1345, King Dušan wrote to the Venetian doge, offering his support in the siege of Zadar.¹²¹ Around the same time, Nikola Buća, Dušan's protovestiarios, also wrote to the doge, informing him that the Serbian king was prepared to send a contingent of at least 500 soldiers at his own expense.¹²² There is little doubt that Dušan believed that demonstrating goodwill toward Venice would benefit him when the time came to seek their naval support for his planned conquest of Constantinople. Venice responded to Dušan the following month, express-

¹¹⁸ Ђирковић, *Историја средњовековне босанске државе*, 114–115; Vjekoslav Klaić, *Povijest Hrvata od najstarijih vremena do svršetka XIX stoljeća, knjiga druga, treće doba: Vladanje kraljeva iz raznih porodica (1301–1526)* (Zagreb: Nakladni zavod MH, 1988), 97–99.

¹¹⁹ Klaić, *Povijest Hrvata II*, 99–100; Nada Klaić, *Povijest Hrvata u razvijenom srednjem vijeku* (Zagreb: Školska knjiga, 1976), 610–611.

¹²⁰ Klaić, *Povijest Hrvata II*, 100–101; Klaić, *Povijest Hrvata*, 612.

¹²¹ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 278–279; Митровић, Кисић Божић, „Писмо краља Стефана Душана“, 9–24; Порчић, Исаиловић, *Документи владара*, 31–33, 228–230.

¹²² Ljubić, *Listine II*, 279; Порчић, Исаиловић, *Документи владара*, 31–32, 438–439.

ing gratitude but declining his offer, stating that they were confident in their ability to swiftly subdue the rebels with their own forces.¹²³

At this time, Venice and Serbia shared a common enemy—Hungary—which made them natural allies. It is well known that Serbia was at war with Hungary in 1346.¹²⁴ An undated letter, likely from that year, reveals that while King Louis I was preparing a campaign against certain invaders in his territories, when Stefan Dušan launched an attack on Hungary.¹²⁵ Unwilling to fight on two fronts, the Hungarian king negotiated a truce with Dušan, which reportedly included a provision for a marriage alliance between Dušan's son, Uroš, and a relative of King Louis.¹²⁶ The exact date of this truce is unknown, but it is reasonable to assume it was signed between April—when Dušan was crowned emperor—and 29 July 1346, when the Venetians anticipated a meeting between the Serbian and Hungarian rulers and urged Dušan to advocate on their behalf.¹²⁷ Furthermore, as early as June of that year, the Serbian king offered to mediate between Venice and Hungary, suggesting that his hostilities with Louis I had already ceased.¹²⁸ Given that the Hungarian king was near Bihać on 27 May, en route to Zadar,¹²⁹ the likely timeframe for the truce can be narrowed to the first half of May 1346.¹³⁰

Even while at war with Hungary, Dušan closely followed events in Dalmatia. In the second half of January 1346, his envoys travelled to Venice via Dubrovnik, where they boarded a galley.¹³¹ In addition to proposing an alliance for a military campaign against Byzantium and Constantinople, the Serbian ruler also offered military assistance for the siege of Zadar. This offer confirms that Dušan was in open conflict with

¹²³ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 289; Ћук, *Србија и Венеција*, 58. On that occasion, they also allowed the Serbian king to acquire some weapons in Venice, Ljubić, *Listine II*, 289.

¹²⁴ Јиречек, *Историја Срба I*, 225.

¹²⁵ Although it is not mentioned who the enemies who invaded Louis's states were, it does not seem impossible that they were the Venetians who were besieging Zadar at that moment.

¹²⁶ Сима Ћирковић, „О једној српско-угарској алијанси“, *Зборник радова Византолошког института* 44 (2007), 412.

¹²⁷ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 365–366; Ћук, *Србија и Венеција*, 59. f. 35.

¹²⁸ Ћук, *Србија и Венеција*, 60.

¹²⁹ Klaić, *Povijest Hrvata II*, 104.

¹³⁰ Ћирковић, „Српско-угарска алијанса“, 417. believed that the marriage contract between Uroš and a relative of the Hungarian king was concluded in the autumn of 1346.

¹³¹ Ћук, *Србија и Венеција*, 59.

Hungary at the time.¹³² Unlike in October of the previous year, Dušan now revealed his true motives—his generosity toward Venice was meant as a reciprocal favour, expecting Venetian support for his own plans in return. On 3 March, Venice responded to Dušan's proposals, rejecting both the alliance and his offer of military assistance.¹³³ Dušan's proposed contribution was likely symbolic, given the significant Venetian forces already stationed at Zadar. Thus, the Serbian Emperor may have seen this offer as a gesture of goodwill, rather than an attempt to make a decisive military impact. However, it also served as leverage, allowing Dušan to expect a favour from the Venetians in return. In this sense, the offer of military support was more of a diplomatic manoeuvre than a genuine desire to aid Venice in the siege.

As we have seen, the war between Serbia and Hungary ended by late spring 1346 or shortly thereafter—certainly before 29 July. Consequently, Dušan could no longer offer military assistance to Venice, but he could still serve as a mediator between the two sides. Mediation by the Serbian emperor would have been advantageous for both parties. Venice was expending significant resources in its war against Zadar and sought to end the conflict swiftly.¹³⁴ Meanwhile, the Hungarian king also wished to conclude hostilities as soon as possible in order to focus on his planned campaign in southern Italy. In June 1346, Dušan sent envoys to Venice to negotiate a peace agreement between the republic and Hungary.¹³⁵ However, their mission proved unsuccessful, and hostilities between Venice and Hungary continued.

From early June 1346, King Louis I of Hungary was stationed near Zadar. The Venetians sent envoys to him, but the Hungarian king refused even to receive them. They then turned to his nobles, particularly ban Stjepan II Kotromanić of Bosnia, hoping to use his influence to persuade the king to negotiate. However, Louis I remained adamant. On 1 July, his army suffered a defeat outside Zadar, prompting the king to

¹³² *Ibid*, 59. About Dušan's conquest plans for Constantinople see Radić, „Venezia, Bisanzio e la Serbia attorno ala metà del XIV secolo“, *Глас CDIV Српске академије наука и уметности, Одељење историјских наука*, књ. 13 (2006), 99.

¹³³ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 326; Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 59–60.

¹³⁴ Klaić, *Povijest Hrvata II*, 110.

¹³⁵ Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 60.

withdraw. At the same time, he rejected a Venetian offer to cede Zadar to them for 60,000 ducats.¹³⁶

By late July, aware that their recent victory had given them a stronger negotiating position with Hungary, the Venetians took decisive steps toward peace efforts. This is evident in their appeal to Dušan as a potential mediator. They wrote to the Serbian emperor, requesting that, should he meet with the Hungarian king, he recommended their envoys to him. Meanwhile, they instructed their own diplomats to seek Dušan's "help, advice, and support, as our honourable and most esteemed friend, in whom we have full hope and trust".¹³⁷ Unfortunately, there is no confirmation that such a meeting between the two rulers ever took place. If it did, it appears that the mediation was unsuccessful, as hostilities between Venice and Hungary continued.

Eventually, as famine struck the city, the citizens of Zadar were forced to surrender. On 15 December 1346, Venice signed a peace treaty with them, though no agreement was reached with the Hungarian king at that time.¹³⁸ Over the next year and a half, relations between Venice and Hungary remained in a state of neither full war nor peace.¹³⁹ It appears that in the spring of 1348, Dušan once again offered to mediate between the two powers. The Venetians accepted his proposal with great appreciation in early April.¹⁴⁰ A truce between Venice and Hungary, set to last for the next eight years, was concluded on 5 August 1348.¹⁴¹ Given Dušan's previous efforts at mediation, it is reasonable to assume that he played a role in this agreement.¹⁴² Additionally, it is likely that,

¹³⁶ Magda Jászay, *Venezia e Ungheria. La storia travagliata di una vicinanza*, Trad. di Annamaria Venturini (Udine: Edizioni del Labirinto, 2004), 50–51; Klaić, *Povijest Hrvata II*, 105–107. The Venetians also offered 100,000 ducats for all of Dalmatia.

¹³⁷ Ljubić, *Listine II*, 365–366; Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 60; Крекић, „Млечи и унутрашњост Балкана“, 154. In addition to Dušan, mediation in the Venetian-Hungarian war was also offered by the Bosnian Ban Stjepan II Kotromanić and Humbert II of Viennois, the last ruler of Dauphiné, Јиречек, *Историја Срба I*, 225.

¹³⁸ Klaić, *Povijest Hrvata II*, 109.

¹³⁹ Klaić, *Povijest Hrvata*, 619.

¹⁴⁰ Ljubić, *Listine III*, 75–76.

¹⁴¹ More about that in Klaić, *Povijest Hrvata II*, 122.

¹⁴² Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 61. There are indications that this was not the first time Dušan mediated in achieving peace that was important to the Venetians. It is possible that in 1343 he played a role in the reconciliation between Venice and the Croatian nobleman

out of respect for the Serbian emperor, the truce also covered his sister, Jelena Šubić, the widow of Mladen III, lord of Omiš, Klis, and Skradin, along with her young son, Mladen IV.¹⁴³

Following a period of relative peace, the final collaboration between Venice and Emperor Dušan occurred in 1355 when Serbia became involved in the Venetian-Hungarian struggle over the cities held by Dušan's sister, Jelena Šubić. After her husband's death during the plague of 1348, Jelena took on the responsibility of defending her son's inheritance.¹⁴⁴

Her son's holdings remained secure while the eight-year truce between Venice and Hungary was in effect. However, before the truce expired, in the spring of 1355, the Hungarian king attempted to acquire the cities through the mediation of the Bosnian ban. At that time, Jelena, the mother of ban Tvrtko I of Bosnia (and the sister of Mladen III Bribirski), visited her namesake in Klis to deliver messages from King Louis I, likely concerning Hungarian demands for the surrender of Omiš, Klis, and Skradin.¹⁴⁵ Meanwhile, the Serbian-Hungarian war, which had begun in the summer of 1354, ended in the spring of 1355.¹⁴⁶ This freed the Hungarian king to focus more on Dalmatia. However, despite his efforts, he was unable to gain control of the desired cities at that time. When Venice signed a peace treaty with Genoa in late spring—ending their concurrent war—the republic also turned its attention to these contested territories.

In early September, with the assistance of Croatian ban Nikola Banić, King Louis managed to seize Omiš. This prompted the Venetians to intensify their efforts to capture the remaining two cities, Klis and Skradin.¹⁴⁷ They sent envoys to negotiate with Jelena about purchasing them, but all attempts to acquire the cities through diplomatic means proved unsuccessful.¹⁴⁸ In this complex situation, Jelena turned to her

Ivan Nelipčić, Небојша Порчић, „Дипломатија државе Немањића“ (магистарски рад, Универзитет у Београду, 2007), 254.

¹⁴³ Жиречек, *Историја Срба I*, 225.

¹⁴⁴ Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 65; Klaić, *Povijest Hrvata II*, 139.

¹⁴⁵ Klaić, *Povijest Hrvata II*, 139.

¹⁴⁶ Ђирковић, „Српско-угарска алијанса“, 412.

¹⁴⁷ Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 65 and f. 65; Klaić, *Povijest Hrvata II*, 139.

¹⁴⁸ Ђук, *Србија и Венеција*, 65–66. The Venetians sent their provveditore, Maffeo Emo, to Jelena, and he managed to negotiate an agreement under which Venice would receive Skradin for ten years and also be entrusted with the defense of Klis. As part of this ar-

brother, Emperor Dušan, for support. By the second half of October, it was already known in Venice that Dušan planned to take control of Klis and Skradin.¹⁴⁹ His forces likely arrived the following month. Knight Palman, a prominent figure in Dušan's service, entered Klis, accompanied by knez Mrcota Mrcotić, while Đuraš Ilijić, along with his son, his brothers Nikola and Blandin, and their sons, took control of Skradin. The arrival of the Serbian army reignited the conflict to the extent that the Venetians briefly considered making peace with the Hungarian king.¹⁵⁰ Croatian ban Nikola Banić, acting on behalf of Louis I, began besieging the cities, focusing particularly on Klis. By late November or early December, his forces had managed to capture the lower town, though the fortress itself remained in the hands of Palman.¹⁵¹

The Venetians soon realised that Dušan was now the key figure in the conflict and that any negotiations for the acquisition of Klis and Skradin would have to go through him. Consequently, during November and December, they sent envoys to the Serbian emperor.¹⁵² The chief negotiator for Venice was the procurator, Jacopo Delfino, who resided at Dušan's court. Initially, he was instructed to offer 100,000 *librarum parvorum* for both cities—60,000 for Klis and 40,000 for Skradin.¹⁵³ However,

rangement, some Venetian troops were stationed in Skradin, where they remained throughout August and September 1355. However, in the end, the agreement did not materialize. Later, the Venetians continued to seek ways to acquire the inheritance of Mladen IV. In mid-October, they offered her 50,000 *librarum parvorum* for Klis, but once again, Jelena refused to accept the offer, Dane Gruber, „Borba Ludovika I s Mlečanima za Dalmaciju (1348–1358)“, *Rad JAZU* 152 (1903), 67–71.

¹⁴⁹ Eager to outmaneuver the Serbian emperor, the Venetians ordered their provveditori in Dalmatia to offer Jelena 70,000 *librarum parvorum* for Klis and up to 40,000 for Skradin. To ensure the success of their plan, they also intended to bribe her men with 3,000 *librarum*, Klaić, *Povijest Hrvata II*, 140.

¹⁵⁰ *Ibid*, 140; Тук, *Србија и Венеција*, 66. and f. 70; Uzelac, „Palman of Letinberch“, 163; Mladen Ančić, „Rat kao organizirani društveni pothvat: Zadarski mir kao rezultat rata za Zadar“, u *Zadarski mir: Prekretnica anžuvinskog doba*, ur. Mladen Ančić, Antun Nekić (Zadar: Sveučilište u Zadru, 2022), 114.

¹⁵¹ Тук, *Србија и Венеција*, 66. and f. 71; Uzelac, „Palman of Letinberch“, 163; Jelena was also staying in Klis at the time, Klaić, *Povijest Hrvata II*, 140.

¹⁵² Тук, *Србија и Венеција*, 66.

¹⁵³ Ljubić, *Listine III*, 297; Тук, *Србија и Венеција*, 66. Two weeks earlier, he had been instructed by Venice not to propose any sum of money, but to inquire into the opinion of

Venice later reconsidered, sending new instructions to Delfino, reducing the offer to 65,000 *librarum parvorum*—40,000 for Klis and 25,000 for Skradin.¹⁵⁴ Around this time, a Serbian envoy visited Venice. While details remain uncertain, it is possible that he informed the Venetians that Dušan was willing to hand over Klis and Skradin to be defended in his name.¹⁵⁵

Meanwhile, the siege of the cities continued. Both sides were eager to gain control as quickly as possible. The Venetians even attempted to bribe Knight Palman into surrendering Klis. By September (or earlier), Venice already had troops stationed in Skradin, and in December, they reinforced their presence with additional detachments. Throughout this time, they continued to supply both cities with provisions and weapons.¹⁵⁶

On January 10, 1356, Đuraš Ilijić decided to surrender Skradin to Venice. It was then revealed that, under Dušan's orders, Ilijić had been entrusted with the city's defence but was instructed to hand it over to the Venetians if he found himself unable to hold it.¹⁵⁷ Rumours of Dušan's death circulated in Skradin at this time, which may have influenced Ilijić's decision to relinquish the city. Regardless, he surrendered Skradin to Venice for safekeeping and defence in the emperor's name. The Venetians swore an oath to return the fortress to Dušan whenever he requested it. Additionally, they promised to provide Ilijić, his brothers, and their families with passage on their ships and a suitable indemnity should the Serbian emperor take issue with their surrendering the city to Venice.¹⁵⁸ As for Klis, Croatian ban Nikola Banić eventually captured it, likely before March 1356.¹⁵⁹ However, the struggle over these two cities was merely a prelude to larger developments in Venetian-Hungarian relations.

the Serbian Emperor and find out what he would ask for in exchange for the cities, Ljubić, *Listine III*, 288; Gruber, „Borba“, 73.

¹⁵⁴ Ljubić, *Listine III*, 299; Тук, *Србија и Венеција*, 66. It is obvious, judging by the amount of money, that the Venetians attached greater importance to Klis.

¹⁵⁵ Gruber, „Borba“, 75.

¹⁵⁶ Тук, *Србија и Венеција*, 66–67.

¹⁵⁷ Ljubić, *Listine III*, 305; Тук, *Србија и Венеција*, 67.

¹⁵⁸ Ljubić, *Listine III*, 304; Тук, *Србија и Венеција*, 67; Gruber, „Borba“, 79.

¹⁵⁹ Тук, *Србија и Венеција*, 67; Uzelac, „Palman of Letinberch“, 163. On January 23, the Venetians wrote to their envoy Jacopo Delfino to return to Venice if his stay at the Serbian court after Dušan's death could no longer be of use., Ljubić, *Listine III*, 308.

Emperor Stefan Dušan passed away on December 20, 1355. In the months following his death, rumours circulated about a possible Serbian-Venetian alliance, though there is little evidence to support this claim.¹⁶⁰ Soon after, a war broke out between Hungary and Venice, ultimately resulting in the expulsion of the Venetians from Dalmatia. This marked the beginning of a long period of stagnation in Serbian-Venetian relations. It would take nearly half a century before these relations became once again significant and dynamic.

Conclusion

Although Serbian-Venetian relations during Dušan's reign had a long prehistory, this period marked their transformation and intensification. The Serbian ruler elevated these relations to a higher level. While the perceived increase in intensity may be partly due to the better preservation of historical sources, it was primarily a consequence of the complex international dynamics of the time. Up until the 1340s, the primary aspect of Serbian-Venetian relations was economic, particularly trade, with political interactions occurring mainly within the Serbia–

¹⁶⁰ King Louis I had allegedly planned to wage war against Serbia again toward the end of Dušan's life. At the beginning of 1356, the Hungarian ruler gathered his army in Zagreb and issued a proclamation stating his desire to conquer the Kingdom of Raška, which had once belonged to his ancestors but was now held by rebellious schismatics. In the spring, he remained committed to these plans, informing the pope of his intention to go to war with Serbia and, once victorious, to convert its population to the Catholic faith. He also communicated with Venice, expressing his willingness to reconcile with the republic—likely in an effort to secure a free hand for his attack on Serbia. However, Louis I soon changed his mind and decided to strike Venice instead. It is also possible that the Hungarian king deliberately misled the Venetians, as Zagreb was hardly a strategic gathering point for an army planning to invade Serbia. In any case, Pope Innocent VI had received reports of some kind of alliance between Venice and Serbia during this period, though it remains uncertain whether such an alliance ever truly existed. It is possible that Louis I justified his attack on Venice by claiming that the Venetians were allied with Serbia. Regardless, on July 17, the pope wrote to the Venetian Doge, Giovanni Gradenigo, regarding the alliance that the Venetians had supposedly formed with the "enemies of God and the Catholics—the king of the schismatic and heretical *Rasenses* (Rascians)"—against Hungary. The pope demanded that the Venetians renounce this alliance, declaring it null and void and condemning it if they refused, Ljubić, *Listine III*, 327. Ultimately, Serbia did not participate in the ensuing war between Venice and Hungary.

Dubrovnik–Venice triangle. While trade remained a significant factor during Dušan's reign, the political dimension became more complex. From Serbia's perspective, it even took precedence: Dušan's expansionist policies drove the Serbian side to cultivate closer ties with Venice. On the other hand, for the Republic of St. Mark, commerce was the primary force shaping international relations. Any political actions Venice undertook concerning Serbia were ultimately aimed at preventing military conflicts, as only in times of peace could its merchants operate without hindrance.

Dušan's motivation for maintaining good relations with Venice was largely rooted in his hope that the Venetians would eventually assist him in capturing Constantinople. A secondary reason was closely linked to this goal: by fostering good relations with Venice—and consequently with Dubrovnik—the Serbian ruler could devote more attention to his eastern policies. Lastly, Venice and Serbia shared a common adversary in Hungary, making their cooperation mutually beneficial. Although Dušan formally proposed an alliance against Byzantium only when preparing for his imperial coronation, he had been laying the groundwork for potential collaboration long before that. By accommodating Venetian interests, he allowed the Venetian-Kotor treaty of 1335 to be concluded at the expense of the people of Kotor and later extended its validity twice. Five years later, the Serbian king offered military support to Venice in case of war and, more importantly, guaranteed free passage for Venetian merchants through his lands. Around that time, he also assured Doge Francesco Dandolo that Venice would be reimbursed for any losses suffered from recent shipwrecks.

During the Venetian-Hungarian war over Zadar, Dušan finally revealed his true ambitions: he proposed an alliance for an attack on Byzantium and offered military support against Hungary. However, the Venetians, as always, remained cautious. By then, they no longer sought to dismantle Byzantium—especially since a weakened Byzantine Empire would likely be replaced by a powerful Serbian Empire. It was unclear whether Venice's privileged position in the Byzantine sphere would be maintained under Serbian rule. Realising that closer ties with Serbia could come at a high price, the Venetians hesitated to accept even military assistance, which, in any case, they did not particularly need. To justify their

refusal of an alliance, they cited their ongoing war with Zadar, as well as their existing treaties with Byzantium, which they had sworn to uphold.

It is noteworthy how much the political landscape of the Balkans had changed compared to just fifty years earlier. At the beginning of the 14th century, Byzantium maintained friendly relations with Serbia and Genoa while being hostile to Venice. Now, the situation was entirely reversed. The Venetian Republic made concerted efforts to preserve peace between Serbia and Byzantium. The same Venetians who had spent decades working to dismantle the Byzantine Empire were now — when the chances of such an outcome were greater than ever — striving to ensure its survival.

Beyond maintaining peace between Serbia and Byzantium, Venice was also invested in peace between Serbia and Bosnia. Securing good relations with the Bosnian ban was crucial for Venice. In addition to the obvious economic incentives, political considerations played a role as well. Venice saw Bosnia as a potential ally in its struggle against Hungary. When war between Bosnia and Serbia seemed imminent, Venice made every effort to prevent it. The republic acted as a key mediator between the two sides, though naturally driven by its interests. However, despite its best efforts, Venice failed to prevent the war. Later, when the Venetians themselves entered into conflict with Hungary, neither ban Tvrtko nor Emperor Uroš would be in a position to assist them.

On the other hand, Dušan actively involved himself in Venetian-Hungarian relations. Unlike the Venetians, he had little to gain from peace between Venice and Hungary. It seems that continued warfare between the two states could have been to his advantage: as long as Hungary remained preoccupied with conflict against the Venetians, the Serbian ruler had more time and opportunity to focus on his expansionist ambitions against the Byzantine Empire. Nevertheless, recognising the strategic importance of Venice as a potential ally, Dušan was the first to offer military support, followed later by mediation. While Venice declined his military assistance, as well as his proposal for an alliance against Byzantium, it eagerly accepted his offers to mediate. After several unsuccessful attempts to reconcile the two sides, Dušan eventually appears to have succeeded.

When hostilities between Hungary and Venice flared up again a few years later, Dušan's continued favour towards the Venetians remained evident, as he vainly hoped that they would one day support his ambitions to rule over Constantine's city. Although he initially refused to cede control of Klis and Skradin to either Venice or Hungary, his instructions to his commanders indicate where his loyalties lay. However, Dušan's death soon followed, and both his successor and Venice found themselves facing the threat of Hungarian aggression. It is possible that at this point, the two states concluded an alliance, but no actual cooperation materialised. Serbia, in the end, was spared, as the Hungarian king directed his full military might against Venice—an event that would have major consequences.

Beyond the mediation efforts mentioned above, cooperation between the two states manifested in other ways as well. One particularly notable aspect was the importation of weaponry from Venice. Although the scarcity of historical sources prevents us from knowing the full extent of Dušan's arms procurement, the available evidence highlights just how significant Venice was in this regard. Dušan also made other acquisitions in Venice and even hired mercenaries through the republic. There is no doubt that for Serbia, the Republic of St. Mark served as a vital link to the West. Additionally, it was an important trade partner. Despite occasional tensions between the two states, Serbia remained a crucial market for Venice, supplying various goods—chiefly products from mining, livestock, and beekeeping. Although Serbian-Venetian relations had been on a steady upward trajectory, a series of unfortunate events at the beginning of Emperor Uroš's reign would abruptly sever these ties.

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МА Милош Војчић
Faculty of Philosophy
University of Belgrade
milosbojic94@gmail.com

Србија и Венеција за владавине Стефана Душана

Током владавине Стефана Душана односи између српске средњовековне државе и Млетачке републике достигли су свој врхунац. У време владавине његових предака, Млечани су се махом јављали или као трговци или као посредници у односима између Србије и Дубровника. Међутим, за владавине Стефана Душана ови односи се мењају и он почиње на Венецијанце да гледа као на потенцијалне савезнике. На овакав став српског владара највише утиче нада да ће му Млечани пружити помоћ у освајању Цариграда. С друге стране, главни интерес Венеције остаје исти као и у претходном периоду: економски развитак и тежња да се трговина несметано одвија. У том смислу, Млетачка република је настојала да допринесе одржавању и успостављању мира на Балканском полуострву посредујући између Србије и Византијског царства, односно Босне. Српски владар се са своје стране трудио да Млечанима изађе у сусрет и помогне њиховим трговцима да намире дугове које су потраживали, односно штете које су претрпели. Ови напори су за последицу имали закључивање уговора између которске комуне и републике Светог Марка. Међутим, услед политичких околности, Душан им није могао изаћи у сусрет по питању својих односа са Византијом и Босном. Тражећи други начин да јој се приближи, понудио је војну помоћ против Угарске, али Венеција је то одбила. Затим јој је понудио посредовање у њеним односима са мађарском краљевином, што је највероватније прихваћено, те можемо претпоставити да је српски владар допринео успостављању мира између две државе. Упркос томе, савез са Венецијом и освајање Цариграда за Стефана Душана је остао само неостварени сан. На крају, његова прерана смрт, заједно са уклањањем Млетачке републике са балканске политичке сцене, спречила је даљи развитак односа двеју држава у овом периоду.